

The Analysis of Store Atmosphere and Shopping Lifestyle Effects In Rubylicious Consumer

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Abstract

Fashion industry is the growth business industry, Rubylicious store is one of this type industry that provides the best quality and creative value by creating the upto date fashion products. The subject of the research is 140 Rubylicious consumers who made unplanned-purchases. Data collection is questionnaires that applies Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The data is analyzed by using IBMSPSS AMOS 21 for Windows. The results conclude that store atmosphere has positive and significant effects on Positive Emotion, and positive emotion has positive and significant effect on impulse buying, however, shopping lifestyle and store atmosphere do not have positive and significant effect on impulse buying.

Keywords: Store Atmosphere, Shopping Lifestyle, Positive Emotion and Impulse Buying

Introduction

The business development in every sector nowadays has changed human life including the consumer behavior that is caused by technology and government policy changes, globalization, the improvement of consumer need, and lifestyle. One of business that has high level of competition is fashion industry. The business industry in Indonesia that contributes to the *Gross Domestic Product (PDB)* is fashion industry. According to *Badan Pusat Statistik*, fashion industry is in the second rank after culinary from the contribution of *Gross Domestic Product (PDB)* in Indonesia. The data of percentage in the contribution of creative economy in Indonesia in 2017 is as follows.

Figure 1. The contribution of Gross Domestic Product (PDB) in Indonesia according to sub sector Year 2017

Source: Badan Ekonomi Kreatif, 2017

Fashion industry is recently developing well. This is triggered by the improvement in middle-class population, the increase of young group income, and the changes of public consumption. Nowadays, the teenagers tend to have shopping lifestyle orientation. Shopping lifestyle is branded-product orientation which is commonly found among teenagers (Patricia and Handayani, 2014).

There are many fashion outlets that offer their products along with the interesting design, affordable prices for all groups ranging from teenagers to adult people. In Surabaya, the fashion product has many new brand products. One of fashion industry in Surabaya is Rubylicious. The store design is interesting and the atmosphere creates coziness for consumer to shop there. The location choice is the area of business activity. For this reason, a fashion business has to make appropriate strategy in the intense of business competition.

Based on the survey conducted by Herlinda entitled the shopping lifestyle of millennial generation in some cities in Indonesia, shows that shopping lifestyle is always following the trend or millennial generation. The percentage of millennial generation who admits for not knowing the income and expenditure to fulfill the shopping lifestyle is 45 % (Herlinda, 2016). Nielsen did a survey on household groceries in big cities in Indonesia, such as Bandung, Jakarta, and Surabaya. The result shows that consumer depends on unplanned purchase, however, planned purchase is not popular in Indonesia in which it contributes only 18 % from the total of frequency in a year (Nielsen, 2017).

Figure 2. The behavior of Consumer Shopping Lifestyle on Household Groceries Year 2017.

Source: Nielsen, 2017

Based on the figure 2, planned purchase in 2017 had lost its relevance. The frequency of planned purchase tend to decrease which was only 7%, on the other hand, unplanned purchase remained stable which was 1%. Unplanned purchase could give 9% of the value (Nielsen, 2017).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Store Atmosphere

Gilbert in (Foster, 2008) states that the store atmosphere is combination of physical message that is designed. The store atmosphere is created as the changes of purchasing plan that produces particular emotional effect and causes shopping behavior. The store atmosphere is commonly called as physical and non-physical elements that influence the behavior of purchasing to the retailer (Eroglu and Machleit, 1989; Hoffman and Turley, 2002 in Francioni *et al.*, 2018). This study focuses on consumer attention on the whole effect of atmosphere on shopping behavior (Bonnin and Goudey, 2012; Mattila and Wirtz, 2001; Michon *et al.*, 2005 in Francioni *et al.*, 2018).

The Element of Store Atmosphere.

Berman and Evans (2010:56), states that store atmosphere consists of four elements:

1. Exterior

The exterior characteristics have strong influence for the store image so that it must be designed well. The combination of this exterior creates the unique, interesting, and prominent exterior and invites people to visit the store.

2. General Interior

According to Berman and Evans (2010) mentions that general exterior is used when consumer is in a store so that many elements influence the brand perception.

3. Store Layout

According to Berman and Evans (2010), store layout includes the design of floor segment, the product clarification, the store control, the room width, mapping store space, the product for individual marketing.

4. Interior Display

Interior display has two purposes that give information to consumer and add the store atmosphere.

Shopping Lifestyle

According to Cobb and Hoyer in Japariato and Sugiharto (2011:33) shopping lifestyle is defined as the behavior shown by the buyer in relation to the respond and personal opinion about the purchase of a product. Cobb and Hoyer in Japariato and Sugiharto (2011:33) the indicator of shopping lifestyle is as follows.

1. Responding to buy every advertisement that offers a product
2. Purchasing the product of new model whenever one sees it
3. Purchasing the most branded product
4. Ensuring that the branded product has the best quality.

Positive Emotion

Positive emotion is positive expression of someone that gives impact on the high demand of shopping intensity (Hetharie, 2012). In general, *the Broaden-and-build theory* aims to describe shape and function from the positive emotion, including happiness, interest, satisfaction, and love (Fredrickson in Rahimi and Bigdeli, 2014). The theory states that the positive emotion experiences expand individual awareness and encourage behaviors and ideas, construct skills and individual resources from time to time (Fredrickson in Rahimi and Bigdeli, 2014).

Impulsive Buying

According to Engel *et al* (2008) states that impulsive buying is a decision made by consumer spontaneously to do shopping activity. The types of unplanned buying are as follow (Peter and Olson, 2013).

1. Impulsive buying
Is the activity of buying that diverges from common buying pattern. This is called escape buying. The buying process is considered unplanned or incidental.
2. Impulsive buying from suggestion
This type of buying happened when consumer doesn't have adequate knowledge about a new product, and consumer sees the product for the first time.
3. Impulsive buying from a reminder
The consumer sees the product and is reminded to buy for inventory at home.
4. Impulsive buying of planned buying
This type of buying happened after seeing and knowing sale condition. For example, certain product with special price or voucher.

The characteristics of impulsive buying

According to Engel *et al.* (2008: 156), impulsive buying has following characteristics.

1. Spontaneity
This buying is unplanned and motivates consumer to buy right away, mostly, as the result of direct visual stimulus on the spot.
2. The power, compulsion, and intensity. There's a motivation to set aside the others and act for a moment.
3. Excitement and stimulation
The sudden urge to buy is often accompanied by high emotions.

Research Method

This is explanatory research using quantitative approach. The data analysis is numeric, calculation, formulation, and statistics data that aim to examine the hypothesis (Sugiyono, 2008). Explanatory research explains the cause-effect relationships between variables through hypothesis testing (Sugiyono, 2008).

Non-probability sampling is used in the research that do not provide equal chance to each aspect or the participants in the population to be chosen as the sample (Sugiyono, 2008). The research method that uses non-probability sampling is an confidential sampling that the sample determination according to criteria, whoever participates in the research in *Rubylicious store* and can be used as the sample based on specified characteristics

Sample determination uses measurement guidelines based on maximum estimation (Ferdinand, 2006).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximum sample measurement} &= \text{the number of indicators} \times 10 \\ &= 14 \times 10 \\ &= 140 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the result of measurement above, the number of samples needed in this research is 140 respondents. The research uses *Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)* by using *AMOS. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)* is statistic method.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To conduct data analysis with *SEM* method, the following stages of testing are needed:

Evaluation of SEM Assumptions

1. Sample Size

The number of data samples has met the *SEM* assumptions, which is 140 data that are in the range of the recommended amount of data 100 to 200.

2. Data Normality Test

Data normality test is evaluated using the *AMOS 21 program*. If a critical ratio is obtained at intervals of -2.58 to 2.58, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Data normality test can be seen in table 1 below.

Table 1. Data Normality Test

Assesment of normality(Group number1)

Variable	Min	Max	Skew	c.r	Kurtosis	c.r
Z1	3,000	5,000	,394	1,903	-,735	-1,776
Z2	1,000	5,000	-,012	-,060	,556	1,342
X21	2,000	5,000	-,099	-,477	-,250	-,605
X22	2,000	5,000	-,060	-,288	-,313	-,755
X23	2,000	5,000	-,180	-,869	-,195	-,471
X24	1,000	5,000	-,336	-1,625	,635	1,534
X11	2,000	5,000	-,395	-1,906	-,238	-,576
X12	2,000	5,000	-,563	-2,721	-,370	-,893
X13	2,000	5,000	-,671	-3,242	,430	1,039
X14	1,000	5,000	-,599	-2,892	-,584	-1,410
X15	2,000	5,000	,136	,655	-,535	-1,292
Y3	1,000	5,000	-,087	-,422	,223	,540
Y2	1,000	5,000	-,755	-3,645	,970	2,344
Y1	3,000	5,000	,221	1,068	-,781	-1,885
multivariate					4,329	1,210

Source:IBMSPSSAMOS21,2019

Table 1 shows that if the value of critical ratio is in the range of -2.58 to 2.58 which is equal to 1,210, the results of these calculations indicate that the data are normally distributed, so that the research data can be analyzed using *Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)*.

3. Evaluate Outliers

Multivariate outliers is done by observing the value of *mahalanobis distance* through the *AMOS* program. *Mahalanobis distance* is calculated using excel in chi-square value at no degrees of 14 indicators at the level of $p < 0.01$ with the formula = $CHIINV(0.01; 14)$, then the result is 29,141. The results of the analysis of the presence or absence of *multivariate outliers* are as follows:

Table 2. Mahalanobis d-squared

Observation Number	Mahalanobis d-squared	p 1	p 2
82	27,395	,017	,911
132	26,858	,020	,774
23	26,607	,022	,586
136	26,438	,023	,395
41	25,929	,026	,312

Sumber: IBMSPSSAMOS21, 2019

Table 2 shows the maximum *mahalanobis distance* which is 27,395. This shows that there is no data greater than 29,141, so there are no *multivariate outliers* in the data and data exclusion is not necessary.

Analysis of Model Interpretation

The results of SEM analysis are as follow.

Figure 3. SEM Test Results

Source: IBMSPSSAMOS21, 2019

Figure 3 explains that *SEM* model can be accepted if the loading factor value > 0.6 . Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that all loading factor values > 0.6 , then the *SEM* model can be accepted. Loading factor is a coefficient that explains the level of relationship of indicators with latent variables.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing is performed to determine the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. The hypothesis can be accepted if the value of C.R. > 1.96 and the probability value (P) 0.05 . Hypothesis test results can be seen in table 3 below.

Table 3. Hypothesis Testing Results

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 – Default Model)

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Positive Emoti <--- Store Atmosphere	,901	,139	6,502	***	par_12
Impulse_Buyin <--- Shopping_Lifestyle	-,972	2,743	-,355	,723	par_11
Impulse_Buyin <--- Store_Atmosphere	1,024	2,685	,381	,703	par_13
Impulse_Buyin <--- Positive_Emotion	,640	,274	2,338	,019	par_14

Source: IBMSPSSAMOS21, 2019

Table 3 shows the following hypothesis testing results:

1. Hypothesis 1 Test Results: Store Atmosphere (X1) affects the Positive Emotion (Z).

Based on the results of data processing, it is known that the value of C.R. $6,502 > 1.96$ and probability (P) $0,000 < 0.05$. This value shows the results that meet the requirements which is less than 0.05, so this hypothesis is accepted.

2. Hypothesis 2 Test Results: Shopping Lifestyle (X2) affects Impulse Buying (Y)

Based on the results of data processing, it is known that the value of C.R. $-0,355 < 1.96$ and probability (P) $0.723 < 0.05$. This value shows the results that do not meet the requirements that is greater than 0.05, so this hypothesis is rejected.

3. Hypothesis 3 Test Results: Store Atmosphere (XI) affects ImpulseBuying (Y)

Based on the results of data processing, it is known that the value of C.R. $0.381 < 1.96$ and probability (P) $0.703 > 0.05$. This value shows the results that do not meet the requirements that is greater than 0.05, so this hypothesis is rejected.

4. Hypothesis 4 Test Results: Positive Emotion (Z) affects ImpulseBuying (Y)

Based on the results of data processing, it is known that the value of C.R. $2.338 > 1.96$ and probability (P) $0.019 < 0.05$. This value shows the results that meet the requirements is less than 0.05, so this hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

The Effect of Store Atmosphere on Positive Emotion.

The results indicate that the store atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on positive emotion. The results of this opinion are reinforced by Sari and Suryani (2013) that store atmosphere is an atmosphere created so that buyers are comfortable to shop. This research is strengthened by the research from Musyaffaq (2017) states that the outlet atmosphere has a positive and significant effect on positive emotions, then positive emotions are accepted as an intervening variable in consumers of *Batik Danar Hadi Surakarta*.

The Effect of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulse Buying

The results indicate that shopping lifestyle has no positive effect and significant to impulse buying. This explanation contradicts previous research by Paramita (2016) that states shopping lifestyle significantly influences the impulsive purchase of BSE City's AEON Department Store on the study entitled *The Effect of Shopping Lifestyle, Store Atmosphere, and Hedonic Shopping Value on Impulsive Purchases of AEON Department Store BSD Customers City*.

The Effect of Store Atmosphere on Impulse Buying

The results prove that store atmosphere does not have a positive and significant effect on impulse buying of *Rubylicious* consumers. This research collaborated with previous research from Rahmayanti (2015) entitled *The Effect of Store Atmosphere Perception on Impulsive Purchases Mediated by Positive Emotions on Consumers in Malang Town Square*. It can be concluded that store atmosphere perception does not directly influence impulsive buying.

The Effect of Positive Emotion on Impulse Buying

The results prove that positive emotion has an influence positive and significant impact on impulse buying. The research is strengthened by the research from Musyaffaq (2017) states that positive emotions have positive and significant effects on impulsive purchases in consumers of *Batik Danar Hadi Surakarta*.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that have been conducted by researchers, the conclusions can be drawn as follows.

1. Store atmosphere has positive and significant effects on positive emotion to *Rubylicious* consumers.
2. Shopping lifestyle does not have positive and significant effects on impulse buying to *Rubylicious* consumers.
3. Store atmosphere does not have positive effect and significant impulse buying to *Rubylicious* consumers.
4. Positive Emotion has positive and significant effects on impulse buying to *Rubylicious* consumers.

Suggestion

The researcher provides some suggestions relating to store atmosphere, shopping lifestyle, positive emotion, and impulse buying to the *Rubylicious* store. The suggestions are as follow.

1. *Rubylicious* should enhance the atmosphere of the shop by enriching the store's design through the use of lighting, music, air conditioning, layout and room color elements. This is expected to increase positive consumer emotions when they are in the store.
2. *Rubylicious* should enhance the positive emotions of consumers by designing attractive shops, product arrangement, and comfortable store atmosphere. Therefore, consumers feel happy and excited to shop and impulsive purchases are increasing.

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